

ROLLING LOAD FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF FULL-SCALE CONCRETE BRIDGE DECK REINFORCED WITH GFRP BARS

Chongxi Gao, Queen's University, Canada, severus.gao@queensu.ca

Amir Fam*, Queen's University, Canada, amir.fam@queensu.ca

*Corresponding Author

ABSTRACT

Recently Queen's University, Canada, completed the first ever full-scale rolling load fatigue test on a large scale bridge deck reinforced by glass fibre-reinforced polymer (GFRP) rebar. One part of the deck was a control section subjected to fixed points pulsating fatigue loading while the other was under rolling load fatigue. Both sections went through 3 million load cycles, and monotonic loading tests were conducted periodically to establish the stiffness. Rolling load has been proven to induce substantially more fatigue damage than pulsating load. This study aims to understand the differences in fatigue mechanism, crack propagation, and stiffness degradation behaviour between GFRP-reinforced bridge decks under pulsating and rolling loads.

KEYWORDS

Rolling Load, Pulsating Load, Fatigue, Bridge Deck, GFRP Rebar, and Full-Scale

INTRODUCTION

As the most vulnerable structural component of a bridge, reinforced concrete (RC) bridge decks suffer faster deterioration as a result of direct exposure to traffic and weather (Nelson et al., 2014). To prolong the service life of newly designed RC bridge decks, researchers have conducted various studies with regard to using glass-fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) as a substitute for traditional steel reinforcement in various forms (Kumar & GangaRao, 1998; Cheng & Karbhari, 2006; El-Ragaby et al., 2007; Richardson et al., 2014). GFRP rebars have a high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent corrosion resistance and do not suffer fatigue damage when the stress level is within 50% of their tensile strength (Benmokrane et al., 1995). However, most of the research on the fatigue behaviour of GFRP rebar RC bridge deck is conducted with fixed-point pulsating load, which has been proven insufficient to simulate fatigue damage induced by rolling traffic load (Perdikaris & Beim, 1988; Sonoda & Horikawa, 1988).

Research conducted by Shigeyuki Mastui concludes that bridge decks subjected to rolling load would form transverse cracks, which would change the local load distribution and result in an accelerated fatigue process compared to bridge decks subjected to pulsating load (Matsui, 1984). Unlike bridge decks under fixed-point pulsating load where the deck resists the external load as a slab, the transverse cracks developed in the bridge deck under rolling load would 'cut' the deck into conceptual beams where most of the external load is resisted (Maeda & Matsui, 1984). Due to this unique fatigue process resulted by rolling load, the bridge deck soffit would form a grid-like cracking pattern, unlike the radial cracking pattern typically found under bridge decks subjected to fixed-point pulsating load. The more extensive cracking propagation would also increase the exposure of internal reinforcement to moisture and de-icing chemicals, accelerating the corrosion process and hence the fatigue progress. As the application of GFRP material in RC bridge decks becomes widespread, it is imminent for engineers to have better knowledge of the fatigue behaviour of bridge decks under realistic rolling load to better design, assess and rehabilitate RC bridge decks with GFRP rebars.

Testing full-scale bridge elements under rolling load requires a special apparatus. The Rolling Load Simulator (ROLLS) at Queen's University, which is the first and only one in Canada, features a vehicle with two half-axles that are equipped with nitrogen-inflated rubber tires (Figure 1(a)). The vehicle is moved by a timing belt that is connected to a 450-horsepower electric motor. The two half-axels are independently controlled by an actuator that is connected to an onboard hydraulic system, where each half-axel can provide a maximum load of 125 kN. At its full moving range of 13.95 m, the ROLLS vehicle can operate at a top speed of 6 m/s.

To study the fatigue behaviour of GFRP rebar reinforced bridge deck under rolling load, a full-size slab-on-girder type bridge was constructed (Figure 1(b)). The RC slab is 15.24 m long, 3.89 m wide and 210 mm deep, resting on two steel girders that are spaced at 3.05 m from centre to centre. Two shear studs are provided every 305 mm on each supporting steel girder to ensure an adequate connection between the slab and the supporting frame (Figure 1(c, d)). The steel girders are connected at both ends as well as midspan with cross bracings to constrain the supporting girders laterally (Figure 1(c)). At both ends of the bridge deck, a section that is 3.81 m long is reinforced with GFRP rebar grids. In the experiment, one end section experiences a fixed-point pulsating load whereas the other experiences rolling load. The design of bridge deck is in accordance with the empirical method in the Canadian Highway Bridge Design Code (CSA Group, 2019). Both end sections experienced 3 million cycles of fatigue loading at a base load level of 90 kN/half-axel.

Figure 1: Photos of Specimen and ROLLS vehicle.

GFRP Reinforcement Design

15M Grade III sand-coated GFRP rebars are used in this study. The manufacturer reported a tensile strength of 1100 MPa and a modulus of elasticity of 60 GPa. Material testing revealed a tensile strength of 1438 MPa and a modulus of elasticity of 62 GPa. The concrete cover on top and bottom of the rebar is 26 and 40 mm, respectively.

The bottom reinforcement features orthotropic rebar grids with 152 mm and 300 mm spacing for

rebars in the transverse and longitudinal directions, respectively. The top reinforcement features an isotropic design with a rebar spacing of 300 mm in both directions. The top and bottom longitudinal rebar extend 600 mm into the middle section of the deck and overlap with other types of reinforcement to ensure adequate development length and continuity of the bridge deck.

Figure 2: GFRP Reinforcement Layout

The reinforcement layout was designed in accordance with the CHBDC (CSA Group, 2019). The reinforcement ratio for the top and bottom in both longitudinal and transverse directions is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Reinforcement Ratio Summary

Top/Bottom	Direction	Design	Reinforcement Ratio
Top	Trans	GFRP rebar with 300 mm spacing	0.41%
	Long	GFRP rebar with 300 mm spacing	0.41%
Bottom	Trans	GFRP rebar with 152.4 mm spacing	0.81%
	Long	GFRP rebar with 300 mm spacing	0.41%

FATIGUE EXPERIMENT

The fatigue experiment adopted a staircase loading pattern, where the load level would increase by 15 kN/half-axel after every 50,000 cycles until it approaches the limit of the ROLLS vehicle. The base load level for this study is 90 kN/half-axel, which is the same load as in a CL-625 design truck with 40% dynamic allowance considered. This method is commonly featured in fatigue studies to accelerate the testing progress, particularly in this case since the frequency of rolling load experiments is practically far lower compared to fixed-point pulsating load experiments (El-Ragaby et al., 2007; Hwang et al., 2010; Kosaka et al., 2018; Abe & Kawai, 2019; Yoshitake & Hasegawa, 2021). The number of cycles conducted at a higher load level would then be converted to the equivalent number of cycles with respect to the base load using the following equation.

$$n_i = \left(\frac{P_j}{P_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{|i|}} \cdot n_j \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

- n_i : number of equivalent cycles at base load
- P_j : specific fatigue load applied
- P_0 : target base load

n_j : number of cycles applied with a specific load
 i : slope from the S-N relationship for RC slabs ($= -0.07835$)

The most commonly adopted value for slope of the S-N curve in Eq. 1 is -0.07835 from Shigeyuki Mastui's study. This conversion equation is based on the Miner's rule of linear fatigue accumulation and has been proven to yield accurate and conservative results (Abe & Kawai, 2019) in rolling load bridge deck fatigue experiments.

Figure 3: Load Setup

A cycle in this study is defined as the process of loading and unloading. A fatigue cycle for the rolling load section starts with the ROLLS vehicle moving towards the rolling load section, which is the loading process for the section. When the ROLLS vehicle reaches the end, it reverses direction and travels away from the rolling load section, which is an unloading process. The ROLLS vehicle would move along a specific zone measuring 8.03 m measured between the centerlines of the ROLLS vehicle in the two extreme positions (see Figure 3), such that the right side half-axle wheels would be 1.1 m from the end of the deck on the right side and the left side half-axle wheels would be 1.1 m from the edge of the pulsating load section on the left side.

The fatigue experiment started with a cycle frequency of 0.1477 Hz and a top speed of 4 m/s, but then was reduced to 0.1068 Hz and 2 m/s, respectively, for a smoother operation of the apparatus. The position vs. time for each scenario is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Position of ROLLS Vehicle from South End of Moving Zone vs. Time

The fixed-point pulsating load would follow the same staircase loading pattern at the same cycling frequency as the rolling load section. The actuator would apply load following half sine wave form with a peak load the same as the rolling load section and minimum load of 3 kN for maintaining contact. The center net deflection of both pulsating and rolling load section vs. time is plotted in Figure 5 for the last fatigue cycle.

Figure 5: Center Net Deflection Vs. Time

MONOTONIC TEST

To obtain stiffness data of the bridge deck, monotonic tests were conducted intermediately during the fatigue test as well as at the beginning of fatigue experiment. The deflection directly under the center of section as well as the deflection of the supporting girders along the longitudinal centerline of each section, were measured using linear potentiometers. Strain gauges were mounted onto GFRP rebars at various locations to measure the transverse and longitudinal strain at the center of each section on the top and bottom reinforcement levels. The transverse strain in the negative moment area at the top reinforcement level is also recorded for analysis.

The pulsating load section monotonic test is simply carried out by the actuator with stroke control at a speed of 0.4 m/min. The rolling load section used a different approach for the monotonic test since the actuator on ROLLS vehicles lacks stroke control functionality. Initially, the monotonic test on the rolling load section is carried out by running singles cycles at various load levels. The ROLLS vehicle would start the test while running a single cycle with a constant load of 10 kN on each half axel. For each subsequent cycle, the load level would increase by 10 kN/half-axel until a cycle is completed with a load level of 90 kN/half-axel. After which, each cycle would reduce the load level by 10 kN/half-axel until a cycle is completed with a load level of 10 kN/half-axel. Before and after the monotonic loading test, the deflection and strain data would be recorded as initial and residual data. Each cycle results in one data point on the load-deflection monotonic test. This method was later replaced with a stationary loading test procedure as the ROLLS vehicle acquired a new ability to apply specific loads with both half-axels, which stay stationary (i.e. use the tires as a vertical loading machine without rolling). To accomplish this, the ROLLS vehicle would be parked at the center of the rolling load section and apply a 10 kN/half-axel load with both half-axels. After reaching the

target load level, both half-axels would lift away to release the load. This loading and unloading process is referred as a load step. The ROLLS vehicle would then repeat the process with the load level increased by 10 kN/half-axel after each step until a load step is completed at 90 kN/half-axel. The ROLLS vehicle would then conduct load steps while reducing the load level by 10 kN/half-axel after each step until a load step is completed at 10 kN/half-axel. Similar to the previous testing procedure, the data prior to and after the loading process is recorded as initial and residual data, respectively.

To ensure that both testing procedures yield similar results, monotonic tests were conducted after 50,000 cycles with both procedures, and the load-deflection data acquired from both tests are shown in Figure 6. At the peak load level of 180 kN, the deflection of the two testing procedures has a difference of 0.11 mm, which is only 4%. The testing revealed that two testing procedure yields similar results.

Figure 6: Load vs Center Net Deflection after 50,000 Cycles

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The testing results up to the first 100,000 actual cycles (407,625 equivalent cycles) are exhibited in this section. The first 50,000 actual cycles were conducted at a load level of 90 kN/half-axle, whereas the later 50,000 actual cycles were conducted at an elevated load level of 105 kN/half-axle. Based on the conversion equation mentioned previously, the 100,000 actual cycles at different load levels are converted to 407,625 cycles with respect to the base load level of 90 kN/half-axel. The load deflection, load strain, as well as stiffness degradation of both sections are captured in monotonic tests. The center net deflection is calculated by subtracting the deflection of the supporting beams from the total deflection measured under the center of each section.

The load-deflection curve for pulsating and rolling load section is shown in Figure 7. The slope of these load-deflection curves are acquired using linear regression analysis and taken as the stiffness of the section. The change of slope of load-deflection curves is a representation of stiffness degradation, while the translational movement of load-deflection curves on the horizontal axis is the result of residual deflection accumulation.

(a) Load Deflection Curve for Pulsating Load Section

(b) Load Deflection Curve for Rolling Load Section

Figure 7: Load Deflection Curves for Pulsating and Rolling Load Section

The normalized live load center net deflection (Δ/Δ_0) change over the number of equivalent cycles is plotted in Figure 8 in both the semi-log scale and the linear scale. It can be noticed that the normalized live load deflection linearly increases on the semi-log scale plot for the pulsating load section, while it increases exponentially for the rolling load section. After 407,625 cycles of rolling load, the live load deflection increased to 2.8 times of its original deflection. For the pulsating load section, the live load deflection increased to 2.0 times of its original deflection. On the linear scale plot, the live load deflection development plateaus after 100,000 cycles for the pulsating load section, whereas the live load deflection keeps increasing for the rolling load section.

Figure 8: Normalized Live Load Center Net Deflection vs. Number of Equivalent Cycles

The increased live load deflection explained above implies that stiffness has reduced. Figure 9 shows the stiffness degradation of the pulsating and rolling load sections over the number of equivalent cycles. Both sections exhibit a linear stiffness degradation pattern on the semi-log scale. The linear scale plot shows that pulsating load section stiffness degradation stabilized after 100,000 cycles, where the degradation continues for the rolling load section. After 407,625 cycles, the stiffness of the rolling load section is reduced to only 36% of its initial level, where the stiffness of the pulsating load section is still above 50% of its initial level.

Figure 9: Normalized Stiffness vs. Number of Equivalent Cycles

A grid-like cracking pattern is observed at the soffit of the rolling load section (Figure 10(a)). This crack pattern represents different fatigue behaviour of the bridge deck under rolling load compared to pulsating load. Towards the end of the section, which is a free edge, a radial cracking pattern is found at the soffit of the rolling load section. The cracking under pulsating load section, however, is governed by longitudinal cracking with some radial cracking towards the north edge of the section (Figure 10(b)). The cracking pattern under rolling loading is much denser than that under pulsating loading.

CONCLUSION

This article presented recent progress on a new experimental study, the first of its kind, conducted on GFRP bar-reinforced full-size bridge deck under both pulsating and realistic rolling cyclic load

fatigue. With the Rolling Load Simulator (ROLLS), the fatigue damage that the bridge deck experiences in real life can be simulated in a controlled environment.

(a) Cracking at the Soffit of Rolling Load Section

(a) Cracking at the Soffit of Pulsating Load Section

Figure 10: Cracking Pattern at the Soffit of the Bridge Deck

After 407,625 cycles at the base load of 90 kN/half-axel, the live load deflection of pulsating and rolling load sections increased to 2 and 2.8 times of its initial value based on the first cycle, which implies that the stiffness of the pulsating and rolling load sections is reduced to 50% and 36% of its initial level based on first cycles, respectively. A dense grid-like cracking pattern was observed on the bottom surface of the rolling load section which resembles the real-world bridge deck observations, where the pulsating load section only suffers fewer cracks, mainly in the longitudinal direction.

The next step of this study is to compare the fatigue behavior of the GFRP reinforced section with that of the steel reinforced section of the bridge after 3 million cycles of load which is beyond the scope of this paper.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.